

IGSN–DataCite Crosswalk Recommendation

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Changelog

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Added DataCite recommended properties and list of Working Group Members.

1 Introduction

An [IGSN-DataCite Partnership Working Group](#) (WG) was formed with the goal of developing a consensus crosswalk to support the translation of current IGSN metadata into the DataCite Schema V4.4. This WG firstly focused on populating the six mandatory DataCite elements (identifier, creator, title, publisher, publicationYear, and resourceType), it then discussed populating the six recommended DataCite elements (subject, contributor, date, relatedIdentifier, description, and geoLocation). The entire WG agreed on the recommendation described here.

1.1 Scope of what is a sample?

Usage: An IGSN ID can be applied to an individual sample, an aggregation of samples, or to a feature-of-interest (the real-world feature that the sample is taken from). An IGSN ID cannot be used for an image of a sample or for digital data.

The above usage contrasts with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) [occurrenceID](#)^[2], where the ID *'records the evidence of the occurrence^[3] of a species (or other taxon) at a particular place on a specified date'*. Note: the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) identifier^[4] can be used to identify digital representations of physical specimens in natural science collections (see Hardisty et al. 2021^[5]).

How IGSN IDs are used is described in Klump et al. (2021)^[6]. It is based on the modelling of a 'FeatureOfInterest' and 'Specimen', as per ISO 19156:2011 (Observations and Measurements, O&M^[7]) and The Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) Ontology (Cox 2020^[8], Haller et al. 2019^[9]). Both ISO 19156:2011 and the SOSA Ontology include a common concept whereby a Specimen (i.e., sample) is a specialization of a larger FeatureOfInterest (e.g., lake, tree, cross-section, transect, borehole, etc.). This Specimen concept also aligns with the definition of 'MaterialSample'^[10] emerging from discussions by a Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) task group.

In the DataCite Schema, the most appropriate `resourceTypeGeneral` for both samples and features-of-interest was agreed to be 'PhysicalObject', which is defined as 'an inanimate, three-dimensional object or substance'¹ and with the examples given of 'artifacts, specimens'. See the [resourceType recommendation](#) below.

1.2 Scope of the metadata mappings

Mappings for the DataCite mandatory and recommended properties are given in Sections 2 and 3, respectively. The WG found that these properties could not be populated using just content from the IGSN Registration Metadata (`IGSNRegistration`^[11]), and so some recommendations also reference IGSN Descriptive Metadata (`IGSNDescriptive`^[12]). The WG used the element names in IGSN Descriptive Metadata Version 1.0 when referring to the descriptive metadata (with a 'namespace' of `IGSNDescriptive`). In practice, these descriptive metadata are less consistent than the registration metadata, varying across IGSN Allocating Agents².

For convenience and consistency, Section 4 gives recommendations for mandatory `IGSNRegistration` elements that are consistent with the other mappings.

Section 5 outlines several possible approaches to supporting sample searches in DataCite services as they are populated with sample metadata following these recommendations.

2 Datacite Mandatory Properties

2.1 DataCite:Identifier

In the case of both newly registered and re-registered IGSN IDs, `DataCite:Identifier` will be automatically populated with a DOI upon the creation of an IGSN ID metadata record within DataCite services. See [Section 2.7](#) for discussion of other identifiers.

¹ At the WG's request, DataCite is to remove the word 'inanimate' from this definition in Metadata Schema 4.5 to include (for example) biological specimens that may still be alive.

² IGSN Descriptive Metadata Version 1.0, developed in 2015, was not universally approved by the IGSN e.V. Therefore, when referring to `IGSNDescriptive`, it may be understood to mean the descriptive metadata schema created and used by an individual IGSN Allocating Agent.

2.2 DataCite:Creator

The `DataCite:Creator` property contains a list of ‘the main researcher(s) involved...in priority order’. For IGSN IDs, this could be the sample collector/creator, chief scientist, curator, or even the person who deposited the sample into a repository. In the case of re-registered IGSN IDs, as no equivalent information is available in `IGSNRegistration`, `DataCite:Creator` will be filed with appropriate content from `IGSNDescriptive` at the discretion of each IGSN Allocating Agent. If no appropriate name is available³, the property will be populated with the name of the IGSN Allocating Agent or an appropriate standard value for unknown information from Table 11 of the DataCite Schema^[13] (page 45).

2.3 DataCite:Title

For re-registered IGSN IDs, `IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` and/or `IGSNDescriptive:identifier`—also referred to as the ‘local sample number’—will be used as the `DataCite:Title` of a resource. Because `DataCite:Title` is highly important for discovery of a metadata record, other appropriate elements that would help find and distinguish a sample should also be included from `IGSNDescriptive` at an IGSN Allocating Agent’s discretion (e.g., `name`, `description`, `resourceTypes`, `material`). If no title information is available, there is the option to fill this property with an appropriate standard value for unknown information from Table 11 of the DataCite Schema^[13] (page 45).

For newly created IGSN IDs in DataCite services, there is no need to add the sample identifier to the title if it is the same as the DOI suffix; however, other local identifier codes should be incorporated.

2.4 DataCite:Publisher

`DataCite:Publisher` contains ‘the name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource’. It directly maps to `IGSNRegistration:registrant`; namely, the organization registering the IGSN ID for the physical sample.

³ As a norm, IGSN Allocating Agents are expected to collect information about the sample owner, Principal Investigator, and/or otherwise.

2.5 DataCite:PublicationYear

The year when the sample was first made available to the research community. For existing IGSN IDs that are re-registered in DataCite services, the year of the `IGSNRegistration:log.logElement.timeStamp` value associated with the first 'registered' or 'submitted'

`IGSNRegistration:log.logElement.event` (these terms are used interchangeably during registration of IGSN IDs) is mapped to `DataCite:PublicationYear`.

For new IGSN IDs, it is likely to be the year at the time the physical sample was registered. Unless, the sample was somehow released before registration of its metadata record.

2.6 DataCite:resourceType and DataCite:resourceTypeGeneral

`DataCite:resourceTypeGeneral` will be 'PhysicalObject' for all (re-)registered IGSN IDs. More specific types from `IGSNDescriptive` or other sources (e.g., ontologies or shared vocabularies) may be used in the optional, free-text `resourceType` property. This will be negotiated with each IGSN Allocating Agent. However, in the absence of an agreed vocabulary, the WG strongly recommends that the terms 'material sample' or 'feature-of-interest' be used in `DataCite:resourceType` to at least distinguish between these sampling concepts.

3 DataCite Recommended Properties

3.1 DataCite:Subject

This free-text property contains the 'subject, keyword, classification code, or key phrase describing the resource'. For IGSN IDs, this is the materials that compose the sample. In particular, for re-registered IGSN IDs, `DataCite:Subject` is equivalent to `IGSNDescriptive:materials`.

Since materials may be categorized under different schemata, the subproperties `DataCite:Subject.subjectScheme` and `DataCite:Subject.schemeURI` should also be included whenever possible.

3.2 DataCite:Contributor

All institutions and people involved in a sample's workflow—from collection to archival (or discarding/destruction)—are captured in the free-text property

`DataCite:Contributor`. If `DataCite:Contributor` is used, then the subproperties `DataCite:Contributor.contributorName` and `DataCite:Contributor.contributorType` are mandatory. For re-registered IGSN IDs, `DataCite:Contributor.contributorName` is equivalent to `IGSNDescriptive:contributors.contributor.name` and `DataCite:Contributor.contributorType` is equivalent to `IGSNDescriptive:contributors.contributor.contributorType`⁴.

Note here that to be included in the reference to a resource, a person or organization must be listed in `DataCite:Creator` (and can then be additionally listed in `DataCite:Contributor`). People and organizations listed only in `DataCite:Contributor` are not included in the resource reference.

Other available `DataCite.Contributor` properties that may be applicable to IGSN IDs are

- `Contributor.contributorName.nameType` – Takes the values 'Personal' (default) or 'Organizational'.
- `Contributor.nameIdentifier` – For example, the contributor's ORCID ID. The name identifier scheme (in this case, 'ORCID') is then expressed in `Contributor.nameIdentifier.nameIdentifierScheme`.
- `Contributor.affiliation` – Free text. For an organizational contributor, this is the name of the formal institution to which it belongs. Should ideally be used alongside `Contributor.affiliation.affiliationIdentifier` to uniquely identify the organizational affiliation according to a scheme (e.g., ROR).

3.3 DataCite:Date

All dates relevant to the material sample. If `DataCite:Date` is used then `DataCite:Date.dateType` (controlled list) is mandatory. For re-registered IGSN IDs, `DataCite:Date = IGSNRegistration:log.timeStamp` with the appropriate `dateType` included (see [4.3 IGSNRegistration:log](#) for more details). Furthermore, if the collection time of the sample has been captured

⁴ `DataCite:Contributor.contributorType` uses a controlled list. The WG is considering if the descriptions of `contributorType` values are restrictive for material samples, and is advising on appropriate revisions to open up their scope.

in `IGSNDescriptive:collectionTime`, then it is mapped to `DataCite:Date[dateType=Collected]`.

3.4 DataCite:alternateIdentifier and DataCite:relatedIdentifier

3.4.1 Legacy handle IGSN IDs

IGSN IDs registered in the IGSN central registry are expected to have at least two identifiers: `IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` and one or more identifiers assigned by a researcher or project (`IGSNDescriptive:identifier`). When an already existing IGSN ID is re-registered in DataCite services, `IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` should be included in the DataCite Schema as follows to maximize discoverability:

1. `DataCite:alternateIdentifier` = `IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` (including the Handle prefix 10273), and with `DataCite:alternateIdentifierType` = 'IGSN'. (Note: both are free text.)
2. `DataCite:relatedIdentifier` = `IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` (free text), `DataCite:relatedIdentifierType` = 'IGSN' (controlled list), and `DataCite:relationType` = 'IsIdenticalTo' (controlled list).

3.4.2 Local identifiers

Researcher/project identifiers are included using the free-text `DataCite:alternateIdentifier` property with the (free-text) value of the `DataCite:alternateIdentifierType` property chosen by the IGSN Allocating Agent. The WG suggests using 'local' as the default value for the latter.

For newly created IGSN IDs, there is no requirement to use the `DataCite:alternateIdentifier` property. But, if any other identifiers exist, then this is where they should be placed with an appropriate `DataCite:alternateIdentifierType`.

3.4.3 Building connections

Connecting samples to one another, and to research based on them, is a primary goal of the IGSN ID. Such connections are captured through `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier`, which lists the globally unique Identifiers assigned to related resources. It is therefore recommended that `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier` is used to the maximum extent possible and is updated on a regular basis.

For re-registered IGSN IDs, all connection information contained in both `IGSNRegistration:relatedResourceIdentifier` and `IGSNDescriptive:relatedIdentifiers.relatedIdentifier` should be mapped to `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier`.

If `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier` is used, then its subproperty `relatedIdentifierType` is mandatory and with values selected from a controlled list that includes 'IGSN'⁵. Again, for re-registered IGSN IDs, any `relatedIdentifierType` in `IGSNRegistration` and `IGSNDescriptive` should be mapped:

1. `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier.RelatedIdentifierType = IGSNRegistration:relatedResourceIdentifier.relatedIdentifierType`
2. `IGSNDescriptive:relatedIdentifiers.relatedIdentifier.identifierType`

The `RelationType` subproperty of `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier` is also mandatory. Taking values from a controlled list, `RelationType` describes relationships between the material sample for which the IGSN ID is being registered and related resources (features-of-interest, parent samples, subsamples, datasets, publications,...). `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier` should be used for any `relationType` listed in [IGSNRegistration Table 3.2](#).

For re-registered IGSN IDs:

1. `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier.RelationType = IGSNRegistration:relatedResourceIdentifier.relationType`
2. `IGSNDescriptive:relatedIdentifiers.relatedIdentifier.relationType`

It is important to note here that `DataCite:RelatedIdentifier` is used for making connections that mirror sample hierarchies. Because the parent IGSN ID is a key element in IGSN ID metadata, for new IGSN IDs created under DataCite services, it is recommended that a child (sub)sample identifies its parent using the `relationType` 'IsPartOf' or 'IsDerivedFrom'. Vice versa, a parent sample can identify its children using 'HasPart' or 'IsSourceOf'⁶.

⁵ Legacy handle IGSN IDs are of `relatedIdentifierType = 'IGSN'`, whereas newly created IGSN IDs in DataCite services are `relatedIdentifierType = 'DOI'`.

⁶ 'HasPart' and 'IsPartOf' are counted in DataCite Event Data, whereas 'IsDerivedFrom' and 'IsSourceOf' are not.

3.5 DataCite:Description

It is valuable to include additional information about a sample, particularly about its 'birth', in `DataCite:Description` (free text). If

`DataCite:Description` is used, then

`DataCite:Description.descriptionType` is mandatory. Values for the latter are selected from a controlled list, with the most relevant for IGSN IDs being

- `Abstract` – Brief description of the resource and the context in which it was created.
- `Methods`, – The methodology employed for the study or research.

Both of these are important for discovery purposes.

For re-registered IGSN IDs:

1. `DataCite:Description[descriptionType=Abstract] = IGSNDescriptive:description`
2. `DataCite:Description[descriptionType=Methods] = IGSNDescriptive:collectionMethods.collectionMethod`

3.6. DataCite:GeoLocation

`DataCite:GeoLocation` is used to encode information on the 'spatial region or named place where the data was gathered or about which the data is focused'. The property can be repeated to indicate a number of different locations, and can express a location as a point, bounding box or polygon, or simply as a free-text description through its (respective) subproperties: `geoLocationPoint`, `geoLocationBox`, `geoLocationPolygon`, and `geoLocationPlace`.

For IGSN IDs, this property will contain where a sample was acquired relative to the Earth or another astronomical object. Note that it may not be relevant for samples that are 'non-geographic' (e.g., a synthetic material).

In general for re-registered IGSN IDs, `DataCite:GeoLocation` is equivalent to `IGSNDescriptive:geoLocations`. More specifically, the following relationships hold:

1. `DataCite:GeoLocation.geoLocationPoint = IGSNDescriptive.geoLocations.geoLocation.geometry[geometryType=Point]`
2. `DataCite:GeoLocation.geoLocationPoint[1..n] = IGSNDescriptive.geoLocations.geoLocation.geometry[geometryType=MultiPoint]`

3. `DataCite:GeoLocation.geoLocationPolygon = IGSNDescriptive.geoLocations.geoLocation.geometry[geometryType=Polygon]`⁷
4. `DataCite:GeoLocation.geoLocationPolygon[1..n] = IGSNDescriptive.geoLocations.geoLocation.geometry[geometryType=MultiPolygon]`
5. `DataCite:GeoLocation.geoLocationPlace = IGSNDescriptive.geoLocations.geoLocation.toponym`

4 IGSNRegistration Mandatory Elements

4.1 IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber

For an already existing IGSN ID, `IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` will be preserved in both `DataCite:relatedIdentifier` and `DataCite:alternateIdentifier`, using the following syntax

1. `DataCite:relatedIdentifier = IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` with `DataCite:relationType = 'IsIdenticalTo'` and `DataCite:relatedIdentifierType = 'IGSN'`.
2. `DataCite:alternateIdentifier = IGSNRegistration:sampleNumber` with `DataCite:alternateIdentifierType = 'IGSN'`.

4.2 IGSNRegistration:registrant

`IGSNRegistration:registrant` maps directly to `DataCite:Publisher`.

4.3 IGSNRegistration:log

The original year in `IGSNRegistration:log` that a metadata record was 'registered' or 'submitted' will be mapped to `DataCite:PublicationYear`. Other `IGSNRegistration:log.logElement.event` values are included in the `DataCite:Date` property using the following mapping to `DataCite:dateType` controlled list values.

⁷ If it can be determined that `geometryType=Polygon` is a box, then

`DataCite:GeoLocation.geoLocationBox = IGSNDescriptive.geoLocations.geoLocation.geometry[geometryType=Polygon]`

IGSN Schema (Registration)	Definition	DataCite Schema
submitted	Date of the initial registration.	Submitted
registered	The object is registered.	Available
updated	Date of the last metadata update.	Updated
deprecated	The entry is no longer relevant (e.g., due to duplicate registration).	Withdrawn
destroyed	The object is destroyed & no longer exists.	— ⁸

5 Searching for Samples in DataCite

One of the goals that the WG discussed at some length was making it possible for people to search DataCite for sample identifiers (i.e., IGSN IDs) in a way similar to searching for datasets, computational notebooks, output management plans, peer reviews, and other resources. Searching for everything in the `resourceTypeGeneral` property with a value of 'PhysicalObject' is not sufficient, as other types of physical objects are also included in DataCite Commons; for example, newspapers. The possibility of adding a new `resourceTypeGeneral`, such as 'sample', was rejected as not being scalable to the variety of object types that may use IGSN IDs in the future.

We expect that the recommendation in Section 2.6 of using 'material sample' or 'feature-of-interest' as the free-text `resourceType` will help address this problem, if it is used consistently.

Additionally—and supported by DataCite and the WG—is that DataCite Members/Consortium Organizations who wish to register IGSN IDs, will create a separate repository(ies)⁹ that holds the metadata records of only those physical samples labelled with an IGSN ID. This can be done without additional costs to these organizations. Even so, the recommended

⁸ A `dateType` that is equivalent to 'destroyed' is required within the controlled list of values for `DataCite:dateType` for when a dataset is lost and a copy can no longer be found. The interim solution is to use `dateType = 'Other'` with 'Destroyed' in the `dateInformation` subproperty.

⁹ In DataCite services, a 'repository' is a metadata record collection registered under a specific, unique DOI prefix (e.g., 10.1234).

resourceType values described above will be required for people to find samples without knowing the sample repository prefixes *a priori*.

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Annex A – Working Group Members

The IGSN–DataCite Partnership Working Group is composed of the following members:

- Lesley Wyborn (Australian Research Data Commons & IGSN e.V.) [Chair]
- Lindsay Powers (United States Geological Survey & IGSN e.V.) [Former Chair]
- Rorie Edmunds (DataCite)
- Kirsten Elger (GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences & IGSN e.V.)
- Fabian Kohlmann (Lithodat Pty Ltd & IGSN e.V.)
- Ted Habermann (Metadata Game Changers & DataCite Metadata WG)
- Steve Richard (U.S. Geoscience Information Network)
- Cody Ross (DataCite) [Ex officio]
- Sarala Wimalaratne (DataCite) [Ex officio]